

Reactions of Diphenylcyclopentadienyln(IV) Chloride

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Diphenylcyclopentadienyln chloride has been found to react metathetically with silver salts of pseudohalides (AgX ; $\text{X} = \text{CN}, \text{N}_3, \text{NCS}$ and NCSe) to give new diphenylcyclopentadienyln(IV) pseudohalides. Ph_2CpSnCl reacts with various neutral donor ligands (L) to give adducts of the type $[\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnCl.L}]$ ($\text{L} = \alpha/\beta/\gamma$ -picoline, aniline, 2,2'-bipyridyl (biy), DMSO, pyridine-*N*-oxide, α -picoline-*N*-oxide and β -picoline-*N*-oxide).

In continuation of our work on synthesis, reactivity, spectroscopic and antimicrobial studies of diphenyltriphenyltin(IV) pseudohalides¹ and phenylcyclopentadienyln carboxylates², we report here the synthesis of some new diphenylcyclopentadienyln pseudohalides and the adducts of diphenylcyclopentadienyln chloride with neutral donor ligands.

Results and Discussion

Metathetical reactions of Ph_2CpSnCl with the silver salts of pseudohalides yield Ph_2CpSnX ($\text{X} = \text{CN}, \text{N}_3, \text{NCS}$ and NCSe) (eq. 1). Ph_2CpSnCl forms adducts with various N- and O-donor ligands at 0° in THF solvent under N_2 atmosphere,

These compounds (Table 1) are white, brown-yellow and pink crystalline solids, stable in dry inert atmosphere. They are soluble in common organic solvents such as acetone,

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF Ph_2CpSnX ($\text{X} = \text{CN}, \text{N}_3, \text{NCS}, \text{NCSe}$) AND $[\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnCl.L}]$

Compd.	M.p. °C	Mol. cond. $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2$ mol^{-1}	Sn% : Found/ (Calcd.)
$\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnN}_3$	290d	1.26	31.30 (31.31)
$\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnNCS}$	175	1.36	30.02 (30.05)
$\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnNCSe}$	90d	1.63	26.82 (26.86)
Ph_2CpSnCN	275d	1.22	32.65 (32.69)
$[\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnN}_3.\text{biy}]$	134d	2.56	22.16 (22.20)
$[\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnCl}.\alpha\text{-picoline}]$	141	3.72	25.20 (25.51)
$[\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnCl}.\beta\text{-picoline}]$	143	2.60	25.35 (25.51)
$[\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnCl}.\gamma\text{-picoline}]$	150	3.12	25.26 (25.51)
$[\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnCl}.\text{aniline}]$	166	4.02	25.42 (25.51)
$[\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnCl}.\text{2,2'-bipyridyl}]$	217	3.74	22.35 (22.47)
$[\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnCl}.\text{DMSO}]$	119	9.57	26.32 (26.36)
$[\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnCl}.\text{Py-}N\text{-oxide}]$	135	9.06	25.36 (25.40)
$[\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnCl}.\alpha\text{-picoline-}N\text{-oxide}]$	136d	9.32	24.33 (24.66)
$[\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnCl}.\beta\text{-picoline-}N\text{-oxide}]$	121d	9.59	24.58 (24.66)

chloroform, DMSO, THF, benzene and nitrobenzene. Molar conductance of $10^{-3}M$ solutions at 30° in nitrobenzene and molecular weights in the same solvent determined cryoscopically indicate their nonelectrolytic and monomeric nature³.

TABLE 2—CHARACTERISTIC IR PEAKS (cm^{-1}) OF Ph_2CpSnX AND $[\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnN}_3.\text{biy}]$

Assignment	X = CN	X = N ₃	X = NCS	X = NCSe	$[\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnN}_3.\text{biy}]$
(C-H) stretch	3 070	3 080	3 070	3 070	3 060
X asym stretch	3 058	3 065	3 050	3 050	3 040
C=C, ring stretch	1 575	1 552	1 560	1 580	1 592
(C-H) in-plane deform,	1 565	1 485	1 480	1 560	1 582
ring breath	1 470	1 430	1 431	1 482	1 565
X asym stretch	1 436	—	—	1 446	1 480
(C-H) out-of-plane deform	1 425	—	—	1 425	1 430
X deform	1 160	1 162	1 155	1 155	1 425
(C-H) in-plane deform,	1 328	1 335	1 332	1 334	—
ring breath	1 260	1 270	—	1 260	1 260
X deform	1 185	1 195	—	1 190	1 155
X asym stretch	1 070	1 090	1 070	1 070	1 074
(C-H) out-of-plane deform	1 020	1 030	1 020	1 020	1 022
X deform	998	1 010	995	1 000	999
$\nu_{\text{asym}} \text{Sn-Cp}$	—	1 305	—	610	1 332
(C-H) out-of-plane deform	800	810	809	815	805
X deform	726	730	725	728	759
X deform	690	700	690	690	728
X deform	—	670	440	440	660
$\nu_{\text{asym}} \text{Sn-Cp}$	—	—	552	554	560

Ir spectra :

In the ir spectra of Ph_2CpSnX ($\text{X} = \text{CN}, \text{N}_3, \text{NCS}, \text{NCSe}$), $[\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnN}_3.\text{biy}]$, $[\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnCl.L}]$ adducts, absorption bands associated with phenyl groups and cyclopentadienyl group, viz. CH stretching, CH-in-plane deformation and C-H out-of-plane deformation appear at their usual positions which overlap each other⁴. (Tables 1 and 2). The other diagnostic modes of vibrations are discussed below.

Ph_2CpSnX and $[\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnN}_3.\text{biy}]$:

The bands of very strong intensity at 2 103, 2 040,

TABLE 3—CHARACTERISTIC IR PEAKS (cm⁻¹) OF [Ph₂CpSnCl.L] COMPLEXES

Assignment	L = α -pic ^a	β -pic ^a	γ -pic	aniline ^a	2,2'-bipy ^a	DMSO ^b	PyNO ^c	α -pico ^d	β -pico ^e
CH stretch	—	3 065	3 068	3 070	3 050	3 060	3 100	3 070	3 075
	3 045	3 050	3 050	3 050	—	3 055	3 075	3 050	3 055
	—	—	—	—	—	2 998	3 040	—	—
C=C, C=N stretch	—	—	1 624	1 585	1 628	1 484	1 630	1 650	1 626
	—	—	1 576	1 480	1 578	1 434	1 470	1 485	1 480
	1 480	1 480	1 501	1 430	1 555	—	1 428	1 468	1 130
ring vibration	—	—	—	1 427	1 475	—	—	1 448	—
	—	—	—	1 192	—	—	—	—	—
(C-H) deform	—	1 460	1 480	—	1 488	—	—	—	—
	1 430	1 430	1 428	—	1 425	—	—	—	—
	1 409	—	—	—	1 411	—	—	—	—
(C-H) in-plane	1 375	—	1 380	—	—	—	—	—	—
	1 332	1 295	1 330	1 330	1 245	1 310	1 220	1 310	1 310
	—	1 260	1 301	1 304	1 132	1 265	1 170	—	1 256
CH ₃ rock, ring breath	1 190	1 190	1 216	1 260	1 082	1 072	1 060	1 068	1 091
	—	—	1 150	1 072	1 075	1 000	—	1 055	1 072
	1 075	1 072	1 065	—	1 035	—	—	999	996
	—	—	—	—	1 015	—	1 222	1 201	1 160
CH ₃ rock, ring breath	1 020	1 050	1 020	1 065	—	1 020	1 018	1 021	1 020
	1 000	925	994	1 020	—	952	992	840	835
(C-H) out-of-plane deform	—	—	—	811	805	812	—	772	810
	805	810	807	740	750	745	835	—	790
	740	795	802	722	725	729	822	740	745
Out-of-plane ring deform	725	740	732	—	—	—	770	730	730
	—	—	—	—	690	695	690	700	695
	—	—	—	—	685	—	670	—	670
asym Sn-Cp	555	550	556	554	550	558	540	—	555

^aNH₂ bend, 1 585; C=C-ring stretch 1 480, 1 430, 1 427; ring + CH stretch 1 192; NH₂ stretch 1 065, ring breath 1 020 cm⁻¹.

^bCH stretch (DMSO) 2 998, C=C and ring stretch 1 484, 1 434; ring breath 1 020; S=O stretch 952; C-S stretch 729 cm⁻¹.

^c(N-O) stretch 1 222; ring breath 1 018; (N-O) def. 735, 822 cm⁻¹

^dC=C + ring stretch 1 650, 1 485, 1 468, 1 448; (N-O) stretch 1 201; (N-O) def. 840 cm⁻¹.

^eC=C + ring stretch 1 626, 1 480, 1 430; (N-O) stretch 1 160; (N-O) def. 835 cm⁻¹.

2 130 and 2 055 cm⁻¹ due to asym. stretching of N₃, NCS, CN and NCSe groups respectively, are attributed to the presence of CN in normal form in Ph₂CpSnCN⁵, N bonded NCX (X = S, Se) in Ph₂CpSnNCS and Ph₂CpSnNCSe^{1,5,6} and covalently bonded N₃ group in Ph₂CpSnN₃^{1,6}. In [Ph₂CpSnN₃.bipy], $\nu_{\text{asym}} \text{N}_3$ appears at 2 048 cm⁻¹ indicating a negative shift on complexation. The appearance of 999 cm⁻¹ band due to pyridine breathing mode (cf. 995 cm⁻¹ in bipy) indicates chelation from both the nitrogens of the ligand⁷.

[Ph₂CpSnCl.L] adducts :

L = Ndonor ligands : The appearance of bands due to C=C, C=N and ring vibrations at 1 480, 1 480 and (1 624, 1 576, 1 501 cm⁻¹) in α -, β - and γ -picoline adducts of Ph₂CpSnCl respectively, indicates the presence of N-coor-

ordinated ligands^{8,9} (cf. 1 590, 1 575 and 1 485 cm⁻¹ in α , β , γ -picoline). The negative shift of (ring + CN stretching) in [Ph₂CpSnCl.aniline] (1 192 cm⁻¹) compared to 1 278 cm⁻¹ in free aniline indicates drainage of electrons from the nitrogen atom of aniline to Sn¹⁰. In [Ph₂CpSnCl.bipy], the C=C, C=N and ring stretchings show positive shift^{8,11} (cf. 1 582, 1 560, 1 540 cm⁻¹ in bipy) and pyridine breathing mode⁷ appears at 1 015 cm⁻¹ indicating chelation from both the nitrogen atoms.

L = Odonor ligands : The $\nu_{\text{S=O}}$ appears at 952 cm⁻¹ in [Ph₂CpSnCl.DMSO] indicating negative shift (cf. $\nu_{\text{S=O}}$ at 1 050 cm⁻¹ in DMSO)¹². In the spectra of PyNO, α -pico and β -pico $\nu_{\text{N=O}}$ appears at 1 265 and 1 275 cm⁻¹ respectively. In the adducts this band undergoes negative shift and appears at 1 222, 1 201 and 1 100 cm⁻¹ respectively¹³.

The lowering of $\nu_{N=O}$ is attributed to oxygen to Sn coordination. In the spectra of PyNO, α -pico and β -pico, the band due to $\delta_{N=O}$ appears at 842 and 838 cm^{-1} respectively. On adduct formation this band appears at 835, 840 and 835 cm^{-1} in $[\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnCl.PyNO}]$, $[\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnCl.pico}]$ and $[\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnCl.}\beta\text{-pico}]$ respectively. The negligible shift of δ_{NO} is in agreement with earlier observations¹.

Sn-Cp absorption : The absorption appearing in the range 540–560 cm^{-1} is probably due to $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{Sn-Cp})$ ¹⁴. However, the possibility of overlapping of this vibration with the ring skeletal vibration mode of ligands can not be ruled out.

¹H nmr spectra :

In the ¹H nmr spectra of the compounds/adducts (Table 4) the lower field multiplet corresponding to *o*-protons appears at $\delta 7.80 \pm 0.16$ and the higher field multiplet corresponding to *m*- and *p*-proton at $\delta 7.33 \pm 0.14$ ^{1,2,15}. The presence of singlets at $\delta 7.15 \pm 0.64$ in the compounds/

adducts indicates occurrence of a fast degenerate metallotropic rearrangement over the cyclopentadienyl ring by 1,2-shift mechanism^{1,2,15}. In the complexes, it has been observed, in general, that protons of the ligands move to varying degrees towards higher field because of the shielding of these protons to different extent by metallic moiety (Sn).

The integration of the peak areas corresponds to the proposed stoichiometry of Ph_2CpSnX , $[\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnN}_3\text{.bipy}]$ and $[\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnCl.L}]$ complexes.

Experimental

Ph_2CpSnCl was prepared by the reported method². KX (X = CN, NCO, NCSe) or NaN_3 were conveniently converted to their respective AgX salts and dried before use. THF (B.D.H.) was distilled over sodium metal. All the reactions and their workup were carried out under N_2 atmosphere and physicochemical measurements were done as

TABLE 4—¹H NMR SPECTRAL DATA (δ) FOR Ph_2CpSnX (X = CN, N_3 , NCS, NCSe), $[\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnCl.L}]^*$

Compd.	C_5H_5	C_6H_5		Py ring	CH_3
		<i>o</i> -protons	<i>m/p</i> -protons		
Ph_2CpSnCN	7.70(s)	7.82(m)	7.43(m)		
$\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnN}_3$	7.79(s)	7.95(m)	7.47(m)		
$\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnNCS}$	7.54(s)	7.83(m)	7.26(m)		
$\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnNCSe}$	7.59(s)	7.84(m)	7.27(m)		
$[\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnN}_3\text{.2,2'-bipyridyl}]^a$	7.56(s)	7.70(m)	7.25(m)	8.48(m) 8.23(s) 8.03(s)	
$[\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnCl.}\alpha\text{-pic}]$	7.05(s)	7.87(m)	7.39(m)	7.28(d) 7.20(m) 7.10(m)	2.56(s)
$[\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnCl.}\beta\text{-pic}]$	6.95(s)	7.78(m)	7.32(m)	8.40(br s) 7.10(m)	2.20(s)
$[\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnCl.}\gamma\text{-pic}]$	6.53(s)	7.65(m)	7.22(m)	7.82(s) 7.08(s)	2.25(s)
$[\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnCl.Aniline}]^b$	6.51(s)	7.85(m)	7.25(m)		
$[\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnCl.2,2'-bipyridyl}]^a$	6.9(s)	7.72(m)	7.20(m)	8.48(d) 8.33(s) 8.25(s)	
$[\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnCl.DMSO}]$	6.92(s)	7.91(m)	7.25(m)	—	2.35(s)
$[\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnCl.PyNO}]$	6.75(s)	7.88(m)	7.21(m)	8.08(m) 7.62(m)	
$[\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnCl.}\beta\text{-pico}]^c$	6.78(s)	7.96(m)	7.20(m)	7.78(m) 6.90(m)	2.13(s)

*¹H nmr (δ) of ligands : 2,2'-bipy Py (¹H) 8.70(d), 8.60(s), 8.35(s), 7.79(m), 7.35(m); α -pic Py (¹H) 8.45(d), 7.47(m), 7.12(m); CH_3 (¹H) 2.80(s), β -pic Py (¹H) 8.50 (br s), 7.40(m); CH_3 (¹H), 2.40(s); γ -pic Py (¹H) 8.10(d), 7.20(d); CH_3 (¹H), 2.30(s); aniline C_6H_5 (¹H), 6.77(m), NH_2 (¹H), 3.35(s); DMSO CH_3 (¹H) 2.50(s); PyNO, Py (¹H), 8.35(m), 7.45(m); β -pic NO, Py (¹H) 8.08(m), 7.10(m); CH_3 (¹H) 2.36(s).

^aThe multiplets corresponding to bipy ligand (appearing at $\delta 7.35$ and 7.79) are probably masked by the multiplets corresponding to *o*-*m/p*-protons multiplets of phenyl protons in $\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnN}_3$, 2,2'-bipy and $\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnCl.2,2'-bipy}$ complexes.

^bPhenyl protons and NH_2 protons appear at $\delta 6.60$ as multiplet and at $\delta 3.20$ as singlet respectively, in $\text{Ph}_2\text{CpSnCl.Aniline}$ adduct.

^cThe multiplets are not well resolved.

reported earlier¹.

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 157 and 577 spectrophotometers. ¹H nmr spectra of Ph₂CpSnNCS and Ph₂CpSnNCSe were recorded at 90 MHz in CDCl₃ + DMSO-d₆, those of Ph₂CpSnN₃ and Ph₂CpSnCN at 60 MHz in acetone-d₆ and those of the neutral adducts in acetone-d₆, CDCl₃ + DMSO-d₆ and CDCl₃ at 90 MHz using TMS as internal standard.

Ph₂CpSnN₃: A solution of Ph₂CpSnCl (3.725 g, 10 mmol) in anhydrous THF (~25 ml) was added to a suspension of AgN₃ (1.500 g, 10 mmol) in the same solvent (~30 ml) dropwise with constant stirring at 0°. The mixture was further stirred for ~6 h at 0°, the precipitated AgCl (1.32 g, 92%) filtered off and the filtrate concentrated to ~6 ml under reduced pressure. Addition of petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) (~15 ml) precipitated a white solid, which was washed with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and dried under reduced pressure (yield 2.28 g, 60%).

[Ph₂CpSnN₃, bipy]: To a solution of Ph₂CpSnN₃ (3.800 g, 10 mmol) in anhydrous THF (~25 ml), was added a THF solution (~25 ml) of 2,2'-bipyridyl (1.560 g, 10 mmol) dropwise with constant stirring at 0°, and the mixture was further stirred for 8 h at 0°. The excess solvent was then removed by distillation under reduced pressure. To the remaining solution (~5 ml) addition of petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) (~15 ml) precipitated a pale yellow solid which was washed with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and dried at 20°/10 mm Hg (yield 0.50 g, 71%).

[Ph₂CpSnCl.DMSO]: To a solution of Ph₂CpSnCl (3.735 g, 10 mmol) in anhydrous THF (~30 ml) was added DMSO (0.780 g, 10 mmol) in THF (~20 ml) dropwise at 0° with constant stirring, and the mixture was further stirred for 5 h at 0°. The solution was then concentrated to ~5 ml under reduced pressure. Addition of petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) precipitated a brown solid which was washed with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and dried at 20°/10 mm Hg (yield 3.66 g, 81%).

For Ph₂CpSnCl.L (L = pyridine-*N*-oxide, α- and β-picoline-*N*-oxide) complexes, in place of petroleum ether, solvent diethyl ether was used for precipitation and washing.

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